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A Comprehensive Evaluation of Fine-Tuned LLMs as AI-Generated Text Detectors under Adversarial and Multi-Domain Conditions

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ABSTRACT The emergence of Large Language Models (LLMs) generating fluent, human-like text increases risks like disinformation, requiring robust detection systems effective across domains and against adversarial attacks such as paraphrasing. We leveraged fine-tuned LLMs for AI-generated text detection, evaluating three strategies: supervised fine-tuning (SFT), SFT combined with Direct Preference Optimization (SFT+DPO), and multi-stage fine-tuning (SFT+SFT). We assess these in single and multi-domain contexts, examining domain impact and robustness against adversarial manipulations. Results indicate that this approach consistently matches or outperforms current methods in the literature. Across four evaluation settings that vary domain overlap and generator overlap, our best detector maintains high F1 under ten adversarial transformations (formatting, spelling perturbations, and semantic rewrites). In the most challenging condition, texts from domains unseen during fine-tuning and generated by unseen models, the top multi-stage configuration achieves an average F1 of 95.25%, outperforming strong zero-shot baselines (Binoculars, RADAR, GLTR) and a supervised RAID leaderboard baseline (e5-small) under the same evaluation protocol. These results highlight the practical robustness and generalization properties of fine-tuned LLM-based detectors rather than proposing a new detection paradigm.

INDEX TERMS Adversarial Manipulation, AI-Generated Text Detection, Domain Generalization, Large Language Models, Robustness

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, natural language processing (NLP) has been revolutionized by transformer-based architectures [1], such as BERT, GPT, and Llama. These Large Language Models (LLMs) achieve state-of-the-art performance in tasks like text generation and classification. Their effectiveness stems from capturing intricate linguistic patterns and contextual relationships via attention mechanisms, generating fluent text often indistinguishable from human writing. Consequently, they are central to various applications, from customer service automation and creative content generation to research assistance and personalized learning. The diffusion of LLMs raises significant concerns, particularly regarding their harmful use to generate dangerous content [2]. For instance, LLMs can create high-quality fake news articles and propagate misinformation campaigns [3]. As these models become more accessible, discerning between human-authored and

AI-generated text is a significant concern for maintaining trust and accountability in digital communication [4]. The development of robust detection systems, as investigated in this study, has direct practical implications for mitigating these risks across multiple sectors, including maintaining academic integrity, combating disinformation on social media platforms, and ensuring the authenticity of journalistic content. Detecting AI-generated text is challenging due to the high fluency and coherence achieved by modern LLMs. While alternative mitigation strategies such as provider-side cryptographic watermarking [5] and metadata provenance frameworks (e.g., C2PA¹) offer robust verification mechanisms, they require universal adoption by AI providers and can be stripped by malicious actors. Consequently, purely text-based, post-hoc detection remains an indispensable layer

¹<https://c2pa.org/>

of defense, especially for uncontrolled, “in-the-wild” content.

This challenge is amplified by adversarial techniques like paraphrasing, which can evade basic detection systems [6], and Reinforcement Learning-based techniques [7]. Furthermore, the variety of textual domains (e.g., news, social media, scientific writing) complicates the development of generalized detection models, as linguistic features and stylistic norms vary widely across contexts [8]. To address these challenges, this study investigates the application of fine-tuning techniques to LLMs for AI-generated text detection. This presents an interesting duality: using LLMs to identify content generated by other LLMs, exploiting their understanding of their own generative patterns. Using LLMs for AI-generated text detection leverages their inherent understanding of linguistic structures gained from pre-training on massive textual data. This deep linguistic knowledge makes them well-suited to distinguish subtle differences between human and AI text. Moreover, their ability to process diverse writing styles and domains makes them promising candidates for developing robust, adaptable classification systems with good performance.

The primary objective of this work is to provide a rigorous and systematic empirical evaluation of fine-tuned LLMs as detectors of AI-generated text under realistic conditions. Rather than introducing a new detection architecture, we focus on analyzing how different fine-tuning strategies, training domain coverage, and sequential training pipelines influence robustness to adversarial manipulation and generalization across unseen domains and generators. We conduct a large-scale, controlled benchmarking study across multiple training configurations, adversarial attack categories, and domain/generalization regimes. This allows us to isolate the effects of fine-tuning strategy, domain diversity, and training sequence, and to extract actionable guidance for informed system design and deployment. In particular, the study reveals how different sequential fine-tuning strategies induce distinct precision-recall trade-offs, exhibit varying sensitivity to semantic versus surface-level attacks, and differ in their ability to generalize across unseen domains and generators. The methodological contribution of the paper lies in this structured comparative analysis and in the derivation of practical insights that can guide the design and deployment of robust detection systems.

Unlike most existing LLM-based detectors, which typically evaluate a single fine-tuning recipe or fixed architecture, this study systematically compares alternative sequential training pipelines under controlled multi-domain and adversarial conditions, enabling new empirical insights into how training order and objective choice affect robustness, generalization, and operating trade-offs. Direct Preference Optimization [9] (DPO) has been proposed as an alternative alignment method that refines model behavior after supervised fine-tuning, and recent work evaluates how DPO interacts with different fine-tuning configurations across diverse tasks [10], [11]. However, its role in sequential fine-

tuning pipelines for robust, multi-domain AI-generated text detection remains underexplored. Therefore, although prior work has explored AI-generated text detection methods, there is still limited systematic evidence on these effects across adversarial and multi-domain settings.

This study aims to fill this gap through a controlled and empirical evaluation. We evaluated three fine-tuning strategies: supervised fine-tuning (SFT) [12], SFT combined with DPO (SFT+DPO), and a multistage fine-tuning approach (SFT+SFT). Each method is tested across single-domain and multi-domain training settings to analyze how domain coverage influences detection performance and generalization ability. In particular, we carried out the evaluation across four settings, comparing against zero-shot methods (Binoculars [13], RADAR [14], GLTR [15]) and supervised methods like fine-tuned e5-small² (a top RAID leaderboard performer³). We also provide the code, datasets, and models⁴.

This work contributes to understanding how LLMs can be leveraged to combat the threats they pose, offering insights into designing more robust and generalizable detection systems.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the research questions that guide our study. Section III reviews related work on AI-generated text detection, robustness, and adversarial attacks. In Section IV, we formalize the detection task and introduce our threshold-based decision rule. Section VI-A describes the construction of the training datasets and multi-domain setups, while Sections VI-B, VI-C, and VI-D detail the adversarial attacks, evaluation settings, and threshold optimization procedure, respectively. We then present the adopted LLM and the fine-tuning methodologies used to build our detectors, followed by an extensive experimental evaluation in Section VIII. Finally, in Section IX, we discuss the conclusions and limitations of our study and outline directions for future work.

II. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study is guided by the following research questions:

- *How effectively can fine-tuned LLMs serve as practical detectors of AI-generated text under realistic operating conditions?* This question is motivated by the growing use of LLM-based detectors, which are often evaluated under limited or idealized conditions in prior work.
- *How resilient are these detectors to common adversarial manipulations?* This addresses known vulnerabilities of existing detectors to paraphrasing and rewriting attacks highlighted in recent studies.
- *How well do different fine-tuning strategies generalize across domains and generating models?* This targets the lack of systematic evidence on domain and gener-

²<https://github.com/menglinzhou/e5-small-lora-ai-generated-detector>

³<https://raid-bench.xyz/leaderboard>

⁴<https://github.com/Marcomurgia97/A-novel-approach-for-AI-detection-content-based-on-fine-tuned-LLMs>

ator generalization in prior LLM-based detection approaches.

- *How do fine-tuned LLM detectors compare with established zero-shot and supervised baselines under identical evaluation conditions?* This responds to the need for controlled and fair benchmarking across different detection paradigms.

III. RELATED WORK

Prior to the widespread adoption of modern LLMs, the detection of machine-generated text and misinformation primarily focused on earlier neural generators and ‘fake news’ classification. These early approaches often relied on traditional machine learning classifiers, recurrent neural networks (RNNs), or early transformer models (e.g., BERT) trained on hand-crafted linguistic features, stylometry, or content veracity [16], [17]. However, the unprecedented fluency and contextual coherence of current LLMs have rendered many of these surface-level and stylistic features obsolete, necessitating a shift towards deep semantic analysis and robustness-oriented detection, as explored in this study. Consequently, the field of AI-generated text detection is rapidly evolving, with methods generally categorized as black-box or white-box. White-box approaches, such as watermarking [5], require internal access to the model’s generation process (e.g., modifying the logit distribution during text generation). While highly effective in controlled environments, they are fundamentally inapplicable in third-party detection scenarios where only the final text is available and the provenance is unknown. Our work, therefore, focuses strictly on the more common black-box scenario, where detectors operate on text without access to the generative model’s internals. This category includes zero-shot techniques that leverage intrinsic statistical properties of machine-generated text, such as GLTR [15], Binoculars [13], and DetectGPT-style detectors [18]. On the other hand, supervised methods train classifiers on labeled examples: these include feature-based classifiers like Ghostbuster [19] and fine-tuned encoder-based models like RoBERTa [14], a direction also explored in works like [20] with their RoBERTa-Ranker. However, the improvement of LLM capabilities has exposed the fragility of many detectors, shifting the research focus towards **robustness and generalization**. A significant body of work now investigates alternative model architectures and training techniques to improve resilience. For instance, adaptive ensembles of fine-tuned transformers have been studied to address performance under out-of-distribution conditions [21], while competitive performance has also been achieved using gated mixture-of-experts architectures [22].

This focus on robustness is motivated by the continuous development of sophisticated evasion techniques [6], [23], [24]. Recent studies explore complex attack scenarios, such as detecting AI contributions within human-AI *hybrid texts* [25]. Works on ‘Adversarial Paraphrasing’ [26] and AI ‘humanizer’ tools [27] demonstrate that even state-of-the-art detectors can be bypassed. This adversarial dynamic

highlights the critical need for robust evaluation benchmarks like RAID [28] and for new detection methods specifically designed for adversarial resilience, which is a central theme of our study.

Recent work has also explored **rewrite-based and self-consistency detection paradigms**, in which an LLM rewrites or paraphrases the input text and detection is performed by measuring semantic divergence, ranking consistency, or distributional shifts between the original and rewritten versions [29], [30]. These approaches are attractive because they can capture higher-level semantic cues that may be less sensitive to surface-level perturbations. However, they typically require additional generation steps at inference time, increasing computational cost and latency, and their performance may depend strongly on the quality and stability of the rewriting model. Moreover, their robustness under strong adversarial manipulation and domain shift remains an open question, as rewriting itself may amplify or obscure adversarial artifacts.

In parallel, **LLM-centric detectors** directly leverage LLMs as classifiers or reasoning agents, either via prompting or fine-tuning [31], [32], [33], [34]. These methods demonstrate promising accuracy and flexibility, but often evaluate a single training configuration or task-specific setup and rarely isolate the effects of different sequential fine-tuning strategies or training objectives on robustness and generalization. Our work complements these paradigms by focusing on a controlled comparison of fine-tuning pipelines within a unified adversarial and multi-domain evaluation framework, enabling deeper analysis of operational trade-offs and deployment-oriented behavior.

Most existing LLM-based detection approaches focus on proposing a specific architecture or a single fine-tuning strategy and typically evaluate performance within a limited or fixed set of domains or perturbations. While preference-based optimization techniques such as DPO have been studied in the broader LLM literature to analyze how preference optimization interacts with supervised fine-tuning across diverse downstream tasks [10], [11], their role within sequential fine-tuning pipelines for AI-generated text detection has not been systematically investigated. In particular, comparisons across alternative sequential training pipelines (e.g., multiple-stage SFT versus SFT followed by preference optimization) and their impact on resilience, generalization, and precision–recall trade-offs under adversarial manipulations and unseen generator settings remain largely unexplored. Our work addresses this gap through a controlled and systematic empirical comparison.

To facilitate a structured comparison with respect to the identified research gaps, Table 1 provides an overview of representative approaches, highlighting their key characteristics and limitations in terms of robustness, generalization, and training strategies. The table also positions our approach with respect to these dimensions.

Our emphasis is on a controlled comparative evaluation of sequential fine-tuning strategies and their behavior under

TABLE 1. Comparison of representative approaches for AI-generated text detection.

Work	Method Type	Adv. Robustness	Cross-domain	Cross-model	Fine-tuning	Key Limitation
DetectGPT	Zero-shot	✗	△	✗	✗	Sensitive to paraphrasing
GLTR	Statistical	✗	✗	✗	✗	Limited to specific models
RoBERTa-based	Supervised	✓	△	✗	Single-step	Poor generalization
Recent LLM-based detectors [31], [32]	LLM-based	△	✗	✗	Single-step	Limited robustness evaluation
The proposed approach	LLM-based	✓	✓	✓	Sequential	Comprehensive evaluation across settings

✓: supported; △: partially supported or limited evaluation; ✗: not supported.

adversarial and multi-domain shifts.

Our study provides:

- 1) A systematic comparison of different **sequential fine-tuning strategies** (SFT+DPO, SFT+SFT) and their impact on robustness.
- 2) An evaluation centered on **adversarial resilience**, a topic of growing importance as highlighted by studies on various attacks [35]. Our work distinguishes itself by testing against ten diverse attack types across four challenging settings.
- 3) A granular analysis of **domain generalization**, investigating the impact of multi-domain training data. This addresses a critical challenge in the field, as the performance of detectors on unseen domains is a known issue, rigorously benchmarked in works like [36]. Our contribution is to examine this problem specifically in the context of fine-tuned LLMs.

However, to the best of our knowledge, no prior work provides a unified evaluation that jointly analyzes adversarial robustness, domain generalization, and sequential fine-tuning strategies under controlled conditions. This gap directly motivates the research questions defined in Section II.

By focusing on these dimensions, our work aims to provide a deeper, more practical understanding of how to build robust and generalizable AI text detectors using modern LLMs.

IV. TASK FORMALIZATION

In this section, we formally define the problem of detecting AI-generated text using fine-tuned LLMs. Our goal is to characterize the detection task under realistic conditions, including variability across domains, generating models, and potential adversarial manipulations. We introduce the notation and assumptions used throughout the paper, and define the classification setting that underlies our experimental evaluation. This formalization provides the foundation for the methodological choices described in the following sections.

⁵<https://mistral.ai/news/announcing-mistral-7b/>

⁶<https://cohere.com/command>

⁷<https://openai.com/index/gpt-4-research/>

⁸<https://mistral.ai/news/mixtral-of-experts/>

⁹<https://platform.openai.com/docs/models>

¹⁰<https://huggingface.co/google/gemma-7b-it>

FIGURE 1. Prompt used for AI-generated text detection.

The primary task in this work is **AI-Generated Text Detection**. We frame this as a binary classification problem. Given an input text document, denoted as x , the objective is to classify it as either human-written or machine-generated. Let the set of possible origin labels be $Y = \{\text{human}, \text{machine}\}$.

We aim to learn a detector function, D , that maps an input text x to its predicted label $\hat{y} \in Y$. In our approach, the detector D is implemented using a fine-tuned LLM, denoted as M . The input text x is embedded within a specific prompt structure, $p(x)$, which is then fed to the LLM (see Figure 1 for the primary prompt used).

The LLM M processes the prompt and generates a response. We base our decision on the model's confidence or likelihood associated with the 'machine' token. More formally, we consider the probability $P_M(\text{machine}|p(x))$ that the model assigns to the 'machine' output token given the prompt. A decision threshold, $\tau \in [0, 1]$, is used to make the final classification \hat{y} :

$$\hat{y} = D(x) = \begin{cases} \text{machine} & \text{if } P_M(\text{machine}|p(x)) \geq \tau \\ \text{human} & \text{if } P_M(\text{machine}|p(x)) < \tau \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Overall, the proposed approach follows a structured pipeline: given an input text, a prompt is constructed and provided to a fine-tuned language model, which outputs a probability of the text being AI-generated. Different fine-tuning strategies are explored to improve robustness and generalization, and a threshold-based decision rule is applied

Training Setup	Domain Composition	Machine Sources (Models)
Single-Domain (<i>Scientific Abstracts</i>)	Source: RAID + M4GT (arXiv) Size: 10,640 Human + 10,640 Machine	GPT-4, GPT-3.5 (Davinci), Llama 3-8B, Llama-Chat, Mistral-7B, Mixtral, Gemma 7B-it, Cohere
Dual-Domain (<i>Scientific Abstracts & Reddit</i>)	Source: RAID + M4GT Size: Abstracts: 5,320 Human / 5,320 Machine Reddit: 5,320 Human / 5,320 Machine (Total: 10,640 Human / 10,640 Machine)	GPT-4, GPT-3.5 (Davinci), Llama 3-8B, Llama-Chat, Mistral-7B, Mixtral, Gemma 7B-it, Cohere
Multi-Domain (<i>RAID 7 Domains</i>)	Source: RAID (<i>Abstracts, News, Poetry, Books, Recipes, Reddit, Wiki</i>) Size: 10,640 Human + 10,640 Machine	GPT-4, GPT-3, Mistral-7B (chat/non-chat), Cohere (chat/non-chat)

FIGURE 2. Composition of the training datasets. We constructed three distinct setups ensuring a balanced distribution of 10,640 Human and 10,640 AI-generated texts in each. The **Multi-Domain** set relies exclusively on RAID sources (Mistral-7B⁹, Cohere⁶, GPT-3 [37], GPT-4⁷). The **Single** and **Dual** sets integrate M4GT data to increase variability, incorporating models like Mixtral⁸, Davinci (GPT-3.5)⁹, and Gemma 7B-it¹⁰. Full details on the exact split between RAID and M4GT samples are available in our repository.

to obtain the final classification. The performance of this pipeline is then evaluated under various settings, including cross-domain, cross-model, and adversarial scenarios.

The following section describes the overall approach and the design of the detection models.

V. THE ADOPTED LARGE LANGUAGE MODEL

This study utilizes Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct¹¹ as a representative LLM to investigate the general potential of such models for AI-generated text detection, rather than seeking the optimal model. Its selection is based on widespread use, accessibility, performance, and its 8B parameter size offering a suitable trade-off for fine-tuning resources. As an Instruct variant refined with methods like SFT and DPO, it is optimized for instruction following, aligning well with our prompt-based detection approach. To carry out the experiments, we used a 4-bit quantized version of the model.

VI. DATASET DESIGN

A. TRAINING SETS

Training datasets for single-, dual-, and multi-domain setups were constructed using unperturbed texts from both RAID [28] and M4GT-bench [38], which are benchmark corpora designed for evaluating machine-generated text detection across diverse domains and generation settings. Each

training set contains 21,280 texts in total, evenly split between human (H) and machine (M) generated samples drawn from RAID and M4GT-bench. All texts are in English. The reason for using non-perturbed data as the training set was to analyze how each attack present in the test set (perturbed text) affected the model. For texts sourced from the RAID dataset, samples generated via sampling decoding [28] were prioritized for their greater variability.

Three training setups were created: **Single-Domain** (Scientific Abstracts), **Dual-Domain** (Scientific Abstracts & Reddit), and **Multi-Domain** (covering 7 distinct RAID domains). The detailed composition of these datasets, including the specific generative models and source distribution, is illustrated in Figure 2.

The use of Scientific Abstracts for the single-domain setting, and Scientific Abstracts combined with Reddit for the dual-domain setting, was intended to assess how exposure to different linguistic registers affects generalization.

To prevent any data leakage between training and evaluation phases, strict isolation protocols were implemented.

For Settings 3 and 4 (Unseen Domains), zero overlap is guaranteed by construction, as the test domains are entirely disjoint from those used during training.

For Settings 1 and 2 (Seen Domains), we enforced mutual exclusivity at the prompt level through programmatic filtering. Specifically, the base prompts and source texts used to generate the evaluation samples were removed from the

¹¹<https://ai.meta.com/blog/meta-llama-3/>

training data. Since generated texts are derived from these prompts, this procedure prevents any overlap between training and test instances.

B. ADVERSARIAL ATTACKS

To evaluate model resilience, we applied ten adversarial attacks sourced from [28]:

- **Alternative Spelling:** Converts American to British English (100% words).
- **Article Deletion:** Removes 50% of articles ('a', 'an', 'the').
- **Add Paragraph:** Inserts double line breaks between 50% of sentences.
- **Upper-Lower:** Inverts the case of the first letter for 50% of words.
- **Whitespace:** Adds extra spaces between 50% of words.
- **Misspelling:** Introduces typos in 50% of words.
- **Homoglyph:** Replaces 100% of letters with visually similar characters.
- **Number:** Randomizes digits within 50% of numbers.
- **Paraphrase:** Rewrites text using T5 models [4] and the *chatgpt_paraphraser_on_T5_base* model¹². With the first, the whole text is rewritten, and with the second, only the 50% of the sentences are re-written.
- **Synonym:** Substitutes words with synonyms using a BERT-based model [39].

Attack execution parameters (percentage targets) follow those used in [28].

C. TEST SET

The evaluation involved four distinct settings designed to test different levels of generalization. These settings are defined by whether the text domain and the generator model were present in the training set ('Seen') or are novel ('Unseen'). The specific composition of each setting, including data sources and model versions, is summarized in Figure 3. Regarding the data provenance for the **Unseen Domains** (Settings 3 and 4), we ensured rigorous sourcing for both human texts and generation prompts: *Reviews* were sourced from RAID, *Wikihow* from M4, while both *Finance* and *Medicine* were drawn from the HC3 dataset. For the *Medicine* domain, human texts underwent additional post-processing to remove formatting artifacts.

Adversarial attacks utilized the source code from [28]. However, paraphrasing for Settings 2-4 (excluding Reviews in Setting 4) employed the *chatgpt_paraphraser_on_T5_base* model due to computational constraints.

For constructing our test set, each domain initially contributed 300 base texts: 150 written by humans and 150 generated by AI. The AI-generated portion was divided equally: 75 texts were created using greedy decoding, while the other 75 utilized sampling. Greedy decoding, with temperature, top_p and frequency_penalty set to 0.0, tends to produce more deterministic and predictable text

by consistently selecting the single most probable next word. In contrast, sampling generation with temperature=1.0, top_p=1.0, and frequency_penalty=0.5 (with the exception for Claude-Sonnet due to its API limitations¹³, with frequency_penalty=0.0) yields more unpredictable and less repetitive results, as it introduces randomness by selecting words based on their probability distribution.

Each clean text (both human-generated and AI-generated) was subjected to all 10 attacks described in Section VI-B. As a result, for each initial clean text, 10 different perturbed versions were created. Our final test set was constructed by combining the original clean texts with all the corresponding attacked variants. For example, Setting 1 involved 1,200 baseline texts (300 texts from each of the 4 domains); applying the 10 attacks to the 1,200 clean texts yielded 12,000 perturbed texts, for a total of 13,200 samples for that setting (clean texts + perturbed texts). Applying the same procedure (generating 1 clean version + 10 attacked versions for each base text) to all base texts and settings, and considering that Setting 2 has only 3 domains (9,900 samples) whereas the others have 4 domains (13,200 samples each), the total corpus consisted of 49,500 samples used for evaluation, with a median text length of 194 words.

D. THRESHOLD OPTIMIZATION SET

To determine the optimal classification threshold (τ) without using the final test data, we created a separate dataset specifically for this purpose, referred to as the *Threshold Optimization Set*. This set was constructed following the exact same methodology as the main test set (described in Section VI-C), mirroring its structure across the four settings (domain/model overlap) and incorporating texts from the same sources (RAID, M4, HC3). The only difference was the number of initial base texts per domain within each setting: here, we used 100 base texts (50 human-written, 50 AI-generated [25 greedy, 25 sampling]), rather than the 300 used for the final test set. Like the main test set, each of these 100 base texts per domain/setting was subjected to all 10 adversarial attacks (Section VI-B). This resulted in a smaller (16.5k samples) and structurally identical, dataset containing both clean and attacked samples (4,400 samples for settings 1,3,4: [100 clean + (100 × 10) attacked] × 4 domains and 3,300 samples for setting 2). This optimization set, reflecting the diversity of conditions including attacks, was used exclusively to find the threshold τ that maximizes the average F1-score across these varied conditions, which was then applied globally in the evaluation. We opted for a single global threshold, as opposed to multiple domain-specific thresholds, for two primary reasons. First, a global threshold represents a realistic deployment scenario where a detector must operate without a priori knowledge of a text's domain. Second, this choice enhances the robustness of the optimization process. Our full Threshold Optimization Set comprises 16.5k samples, providing a stable basis for finding

¹²https://huggingface.co/humarin/chatgpt_paraphraser_on_T5_base

¹³<https://www.anthropic.com/api>

Setting Name	Domain Type (Test data)	Machine Source (Test data)
Setting 1 (Seen Domains / Seen Models)	Wikipedia, Reddit, Abstracts, Recipes (Source: RAID)	GPT-3, GPT-4, Cohere, Mistral (Source: RAID)
Setting 2 (Seen Domains / Unseen Models)	Wikipedia, Reddit, Abstracts (Source: RAID)	Gemini (Pro/Flash), Claude 3.5 Sonnet, DeepSeek-V3
Setting 3 (Unseen Domains / Unseen Models)	Reviews, Wikihow, Finance, Medicine (Source: RAID, M4, HC3)	Gemini (Pro/Flash), Claude 3.5 Sonnet, DeepSeek-V3
Setting 4 (Unseen Domains / Seen Models)	Reviews, Wikihow, Finance, Medicine (Source: RAID, M4, HC3)	GPT-3, GPT-4, Cohere, Mistral (Source: RAID)

FIGURE 3. Summary of the four evaluation settings. The settings are categorized by whether the test data originates from domains or generator models present in the training set ('Seen') or novel ones ('Unseen'). Dataset sources indicate the origin: RAID [28], M4 [40], and HC3 [41]. For the **Unseen Models** (Settings 2 and 3), we utilized specific recent versions: **Gemini** (2.0-flash-exp, 1.5-flash, 1.5-flash-8b)¹⁴, **DeepSeek-V3** [42] (via DeepInfra API¹⁵), and **Claude 3.5 Sonnet** (version 20241022)¹⁶.

a decision threshold. In contrast, optimizing on domain-specific subsets inherently fragments the optimization data (reducing available samples to 2.2k per domain), increasing the risk of overfitting to the incidental characteristics of smaller samples. To validate this choice, we compared the two strategies using our best-performing model. Results confirmed that the global threshold yielded superior average F1-scores in both a seen-domain and in an unseen-domain scenario. For instance, on Abstract domain (Settings 1 & 2), the global threshold achieved 96.88% compared to 96.73% with a domain-specific threshold. Notably, on the Medicine domain (Settings 3 & 4), the performance gap widened further in favor of the global approach (93.01% vs. 92.18%). This justifies our choice of a global threshold rather than a domain-specific threshold.

VII. METHODOLOGIES

The methodology is designed to explore how different fine-tuning strategies and training setups influence the models' ability to perform accurate detection, particularly in the presence of adversarially manipulated text.

A. PROMPT DESIGN

Given the relatively straightforward nature of the binary classification task (human vs. machine), we adopted a direct prompt, shown in Figure 1. The same prompt was utilized during both the fine-tuning and inference stages to ensure consistency. We conducted preliminary experiments to assess the model's sensitivity to prompt variations. Specifically, we compared the adopted prompt against more verbose formulations designed to explicitly guide the model's reasoning. A representative example of such alternative prompts is shown in Figure 4.

We observed negligible performance differences between complex and concise prompts on a validation subset. This resilience is attributed to the adopted fine-tuning strategies (SFT and DPO). Unlike zero-shot inference, where the prompt's specific wording is crucial for guiding the model, fine-tuning adapts the model's parameters to the task itself, significantly reducing the reliance on prompt engineering. Consequently, since elaborate instructions proved unnecessary, we selected the concise prompt to minimize token usage and maximize inference efficiency.

B. FINE-TUNING TECHNIQUES

We explored three fine-tuning strategies:

- **Supervised Fine-Tuning (SFT):** Fine-tuning a pre-trained LLM using <prompt, label> pairs (label: *ma-*

¹⁴<https://ai.google.dev/gemini-api/docs/models/gemini?hl=it>

¹⁵<https://deepinfra.com/>

¹⁶<https://www.anthropic.com/claude/sonnet>

You are tasked with analyzing the following text:

```
<text_to_detect>
```

Your goal is to determine whether this text was authored by a human or generated by an AI language model (e.g., a large language model designed to mimic human writing).

To do this, carefully consider aspects such as language patterns, coherence, complexity, and any subtle cues that might indicate artificial generation, like unusual phrasing or repetitive structures.

Provide your answer by responding solely with "human" if the text was written by a person, or "machine" if it appears to be generated by an AI.

FIGURE 4. Verbose version of the prompt.

chine or *human*) to optimize for AI-generated text detection.

- SFT Combined with Direct Preference Optimization (SFT+DPO):** We integrated SFT with DPO, a reinforcement learning technique designed for training models on data structured as ‘<prompt, chosen, rejected>’ triples. DPO trains the model using these triples to increase the probability assigned to the chosen label compared to the rejected one, rewarding the chosen label while penalizing the rejected one for that specific prompt. The datasets for the DPO training used the same text as SFT, adapted to this format: for human input, chosen=‘human’/rejected=‘machine’; for AI input, chosen=‘machine’/rejected=‘human’. We explored two combinations: 1) SFT on 7 domains and then DPO on 2 domains (Abstracts, Reddit) and 2) SFT on 2 domains (Abstracts, Reddit) and then DPO on 7 domains.
- Multi-stage SFT (SFT+SFT):** Performing a second SFT stage using weights from an initial SFT stage.

For both the SFT+DPO and SFT+SFT fine-tuning strategies, we employed a sequential, multi-stage training process. In the SFT+DPO pipeline, the DPO step followed a single-stage SFT, which was performed using either Multi-Domain or Dual-Domain data. In the SFT+SFT approach, a second round of SFT was initiated using the model weights obtained from the first SFT stage. For the DPO phase, the initial SFT model also served as the reference model, with the beta parameter set to 0.1. This structured training procedure enabled us to isolate the effects of different fine-tuning strategies and to evaluate how the domain scope, between initial and subsequent stages, influences the final detector’s performance.

The choice of fine-tuning order is motivated by the need to probe different learning dynamics in sequential adaptation. Training from a smaller domain set to a broader multi-domain set (2-domain → 7-domain) reflects a curriculum-style expansion of domain diversity [43], allowing the model to first stabilize on simpler or more homogeneous data and then progressively incorporate heterogeneous linguistic patterns. This setting tests whether gradual exposure improves generalization and robustness to adversarial perturbations.

Conversely, the reverse order (7-domain → 2-domain) evaluates the effects of specialization after broad training. This configuration probes potential trade-offs between domain specialization and catastrophic forgetting [44], and assesses whether narrowing the training distribution improves in-domain performance at the expense of cross-domain robustness. Comparing these two sequences enables a controlled analysis of how training order influences stability, generalization behavior, and robustness in fine-tuned LLM-based detectors.

Fine-tuning was conducted on an L4 GPU using the Unsloth library [45] and the QLoRA framework [46], a Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PeFT) technique [47]. Each model was trained for one epoch with a batch size of 1 and gradient accumulation over 4 steps. It is worth noting that even though only one epoch was used, preliminary experiments showed that training with more than one epoch did not lead to improvements in performance. We used the 8-bit AdamW optimizer along with a linear learning rate scheduler. The learning rate was set to 2e-4 during the SFT stages and reduced to 5e-6 for the DPO phase. Weight decay was set to 0.001 during SFT and 0.0 during DPO.

To ensure the reproducibility of our detection results and eliminate inference-time variance, all fine-tuned LLM detectors were evaluated using temperature set to 0. This guarantees deterministic outputs given the same input text.

VIII. RESULTS

This section presents experimental results evaluating our fine-tuned LLM detectors against zero-shot and supervised baselines. Performance is analyzed across the four test settings (Section VI-C), emphasizing robustness to adversarial attacks grouped into Format, Spelling, and Semantic categories explained below.

A. METRICS

The evaluation uses Precision (P), Recall (R) and F1-score (F1). Precision measures the proportion of texts predicted as AI-generated that are correctly classified, while Recall quantifies the proportion of AI-generated texts that are successfully detected. The F1-score represents the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, providing a balanced evaluation

of detection performance, particularly under class-balanced settings. A single optimal threshold (τ), determined by maximizing the F1-score on the distinct *Threshold Optimization Set* (described in Section VI-D), is applied globally. We iterated through potential threshold values derived from the model's output scores on the Threshold Optimization Set. For each candidate threshold, we classified all instances and calculated the corresponding F1-score against the ground truth. The threshold yielding the highest F1-score was ultimately selected for use in all test evaluations.

Classification follows the score threshold rule from Section IV. In addition to the overall P, R, and F1 results, we provide a more granular analysis by presenting results separately for texts generated using greedy decoding versus sampling. These are reported as F1-Greedy (F1_G) and F1-Sampling (F1_S) scores, along with corresponding Recall-Greedy (R_G) and Recall-Sampling (R_S) and precision P values. This allows for a detailed assessment of model robustness to different generation strategies. For each experimental setting presented subsequently (Sections VIII-D to VIII-G), performance metrics are detailed across three dedicated tables:

- The first table reports the overall average metrics (F1, P, R) across all attacks and domains within the setting. The employed test set corresponds to 13,200 samples for Settings 1, 3, 4, and 9,900 samples for Setting 2.
- The second table focuses specifically on performance concerning greedy decoding. It reports F1_G, P, and R_G. These metrics are calculated by considering the human texts and the subset of machine-generated texts produced via greedy decoding. The employed test set corresponds to 9,900 samples for Settings 1, 3, 4, and 7,425 samples for Setting 2.
- The third table focuses specifically on performance concerning sampling decoding. It reports F1_S, P, and R_S. These metrics are calculated by considering the human texts and the subset of machine-generated texts produced via sampling decoding. The employed test set corresponds to 9,900 samples for Settings 1, 3, 4, and 7,425 samples for Setting 2.

The last two tables specifically compare the detector's ability to classify texts generated using greedy decoding versus sampling decoding.

B. BASELINES

The baselines we compare our methods to were introduced in Section II and Section III (RADAR, GLTR, Binoculars with 4-bit quantized Falcon-7B variants¹⁷). While DetectGPT provides strong theoretical grounding by measuring probability curvature, it requires generating and scoring a large number of perturbed variants for each candidate text, often on the order of tens to hundreds of perturbations, resulting in multiple forward passes per sample and significantly higher computational cost compared to standard zero-shot

detectors [48], [49]. This introduces a prohibitive computational bottleneck for real-time applications and large-scale adversarial evaluations. Consequently, in our empirical evaluation, we selected Binoculars and GLTR as representative zero-shot baselines, as they provide complementary zero-shot statistical signals without the substantial inference-time overhead. We also employed a supervised baseline (fine-tuned e5-small from the RAID leaderboard). The e5-small baseline was trained on a large Twitter-RAID dataset (10,000 original tweets, 10,000 rewritten tweets, 80,000 human texts, and 128,000 AI texts from all domains and models in the RAID), sharing the same RAID source as our smaller training sets, allowing comparison despite the difference in training data scale. However, it is important to note the significant scale difference: the e5-small model was exposed to approximately 228,000 samples, roughly an order of magnitude more data than our fine-tuning sets (~21,000 samples). While this creates an asymmetry, it allows us to evaluate data efficiency. Outperforming a baseline trained on massive data demonstrates that the LLM's vast pre-trained knowledge effectively bridges the data gap, enabling robust detection without the need for extensive labeled datasets.

C. ATTACK CATEGORIES AND PERFORMANCE METRICS

The ten adversarial attacks were grouped into three categories:

- **Format Modifications:** Whitespace insertion, article deletion, number randomization, case inversion (upper/lower), and paragraph insertion.
- **Spelling Variations:** Misspelling (perplexity-based), alternative spelling (British/American English), and homograph substitution.
- **Semantic Variations:** Paraphrasing and synonym substitution.

The LLM-based methods evaluated below were trained using the datasets corresponding to their configurations (Single-Domain, DualDomain, MultiDomain) as described in Section VI-A. For each test setting (Section VI-C), we report the average metrics across the constituent attacks within that category. The nomenclature for our LLM-based methods in the results tables is:

- **SFT-2-to-7-DPO:** SFT (2 domains) -> DPO (7 domains).
- **SFT-7-to-2-DPO:** SFT (7 domains) -> DPO (2 domains).
- **SFT-7D-to-2D:** Multi-stage SFT (7 -> 2 domains).
- **SFT-2D-to-7D:** Multi-stage SFT (2 -> 7 domains).
- **DualDomain:** SFT on two domains (Abstracts, Reddit).
- **MultiDomain:** SFT on seven domains.
- **SingleDomain:** SFT on one domain (Abstracts).

Detailed per-attack and per-domain results are available in our repository mentioned in Section II.

D. SETTING 1

¹⁷<https://github.com/ahans30/Binoculars>

TABLE 2. Average Original F1-Score, Precision (P), and Recall (R) across domains for setting 1. Models sorted by overall average Original F1-score. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R
SFT-2D-to-7D	98.14	98.99	97.33	88.88	95.47	83.75	97.68	98.83	96.63	95.25	96.87	93.78	94.99	97.54	92.87
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	97.56	98.51	96.66	88.49	90.73	87.42	96.65	97.16	96.27	94.36	95.83	93.11	94.26	95.56	93.36
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	96.92	96.57	97.33	86.16	83.00	90.83	96.59	95.86	97.40	93.54	91.69	96.06	93.30	91.78	95.40
MultiDomain	96.65	98.67	94.83	86.87	95.52	80.75	95.87	98.16	93.90	93.12	97.38	89.55	93.13	97.43	89.76
SFT-7D-to-2D	96.25	99.80	93.16	82.02	92.93	75.75	95.26	98.31	92.67	91.92	97.47	87.56	91.36	97.12	87.28
DualDomain	94.23	98.10	91.00	77.92	82.93	77.67	91.98	94.22	90.67	89.31	97.23	83.44	88.36	93.12	85.69
e5	95.84	95.57	96.17	89.91	89.90	90.16	95.92	95.95	95.97	68.70	97.31	66.72	87.59	94.68	87.26
SingleDomain	87.26	86.69	90.16	76.45	72.26	85.75	85.21	82.29	90.93	84.91	83.53	88.44	83.46	81.19	88.82
Binoculars	82.81	82.67	83.16	67.90	76.35	70.42	84.32	91.11	78.97	75.04	80.87	71.11	77.52	82.75	75.91
RADAR	78.88	76.25	84.67	72.91	66.12	85.67	76.58	71.36	86.20	74.68	67.82	89.22	75.76	70.39	86.44
GLTR	69.58	60.10	85.33	69.19	61.03	85.17	70.76	63.65	83.23	67.51	56.73	86.50	69.26	60.38	85.06

TABLE 3. Average F1-Greedy Score (F1_G), Precision (P), and Recall-Greedy (R_G) across domains for setting 1. Models sorted by overall average F1_G. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G
SFT-2D-to-7D	98.99	98.99	99.00	93.70	95.47	92.00	98.65	98.83	98.47	97.37	96.87	97.89	97.18	97.54	96.84
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	98.25	98.51	98.00	92.18	90.73	93.67	97.38	97.16	97.60	96.63	95.83	97.44	96.11	95.56	96.68
MultiDomain	98.33	98.67	98.00	91.78	95.52	88.33	97.54	98.16	96.93	96.40	97.38	95.44	96.02	97.43	94.68
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	97.77	96.57	99.00	89.24	83.00	96.50	97.44	95.86	99.07	95.05	91.69	98.67	94.87	91.78	98.31
SFT-7D-to-2D	97.86	99.80	96.00	88.24	92.93	84.00	96.90	98.31	95.53	95.53	97.47	93.67	94.63	97.12	92.30
DualDomain	96.53	98.10	95.00	83.79	82.93	84.67	94.11	94.22	94.00	93.36	97.23	89.78	91.95	93.12	90.86
e5	96.94	95.57	98.34	92.54	89.90	95.33	97.03	95.95	98.13	80.74	97.31	69.00	91.81	94.68	90.20
Binoculars	90.52	82.67	100.00	82.26	76.35	89.17	94.83	91.11	98.87	85.19	80.87	90.00	88.20	82.75	94.51
SingleDomain	90.20	86.69	94.00	80.62	72.26	91.17	87.55	82.29	93.53	87.91	83.53	92.78	86.57	81.19	92.87
RADAR	84.33	76.25	94.34	77.23	66.12	92.83	81.75	71.36	95.67	79.52	67.82	96.11	80.71	70.39	94.74
GLTR	74.70	60.10	98.67	75.12	61.03	97.67	77.28	63.65	98.33	71.80	56.73	97.78	74.72	60.38	98.11

Setting 1 (Seen Domains/Models) established the baseline performance on familiar data. As detailed in Tables 2, 3 and 4, fine-tuned LLMs demonstrate superior resilience compared to baselines, particularly under adversarial conditions.

The results underscore the value of diverse training data: the SFT-2D-to-7D model achieves the best overall stability (Avg F1: 94.99%), and generally, multi-domain training yields better generalization than single-domain setups. A critical insight emerges from the analysis of attack types. While Semantic Variations (paraphrasing) remain the most challenging attack for all detectors due to the structural rewriting of text, Spelling Variations reveal a distinct advantage of LLMs. Under spelling attacks, the encoder-based baseline e5-small suffers a severe performance degradation (F1 drops to ~68%), suggesting it relies heavily on precise token matching. In contrast, our fine-tuned LLMs maintain high performance (>93% F1), likely leveraging their pre-trained semantic understanding to ignore surface-level perturbations. Furthermore, supervised LLMs consistently outperform zero-shot methods (RADAR, GLTR) even when trained on a single domain, highlighting the efficacy of the fine-tuning approach.

Comparing performance on Greedy (Table 3) versus Sampling (Table 4) decoding reveals the models' sensitivity to

text entropy. Under Greedy decoding, which produces more predictable and repetitive text, DPO-enhanced models (e.g., SFT-2-to-7-DPO) excel specifically in Recall, effectively minimizing false negatives. However, the transition to Sampling decoding acts as a stress test for detector stability. Here, the robustness gap widens significantly. Zero-shot methods like Binoculars exhibit a "brittleness" to higher-entropy text, suffering a substantial performance collapse (F1 drops from ~88% in greedy to ~67% in sampling). Conversely, our fine-tuned LLMs exhibit remarkable stability, with performance drops limited to ~4-5%. This suggests that while zero-shot methods may rely on the low-perplexity artifacts typical of greedy decoding, fine-tuned LLMs have learned to detect more invariant "machine signatures" that persist even when sampling introduces variability.

E. SETTING 2

Setting 2 (Seen Domains/Unseen Models) tested the detectors' ability to generalize to novel generator architectures (e.g., Gemini, Claude) not seen during training. LLM-based methods, particularly multi-stage/multi-domain ones, again show superior performance over baselines, as shown in Tables 5, 6 and 7.

A main finding in this setting is the hierarchy of gener-

TABLE 4. Average F1-Sampling Score (F1_S), Precision (P), and Recall-Sampling (R_S) across domains for setting 1. Models sorted by overall average F1_S. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S
SFT-2D-to-7D	97.30	98.99	95.67	84.32	95.47	75.50	96.77	98.83	94.80	93.13	96.87	89.67	92.88	97.54	88.91
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	96.90	98.51	95.33	85.68	90.73	81.17	96.04	97.16	94.93	92.17	95.83	88.78	92.70	95.56	90.05
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	96.11	96.57	95.67	84.07	83.00	85.17	95.80	95.86	95.73	92.56	91.69	93.45	92.14	91.78	92.50
MultiDomain	95.04	98.67	91.67	82.86	95.52	73.17	94.37	98.16	90.87	90.00	97.38	83.67	90.57	97.43	84.84
SFT-7D-to-2D	94.83	99.80	90.33	78.20	92.93	67.50	93.86	98.31	89.80	88.74	97.47	81.44	88.91	97.12	82.27
e5	94.78	95.57	94.00	87.38	89.90	85.00	94.86	95.95	93.80	77.54	97.31	64.44	88.64	94.68	84.31
DualDomain	92.22	98.10	87.00	76.31	82.93	70.67	90.65	94.22	87.33	86.01	97.23	77.11	86.30	93.12	80.53
SingleDomain	86.51	86.69	86.33	76.09	72.26	80.33	85.20	82.29	88.33	83.82	83.53	84.11	82.90	81.19	84.78
RADAR	75.62	76.25	75.00	71.78	66.12	78.50	73.95	71.36	76.73	74.37	67.82	82.33	73.93	70.39	78.14
Binoculars	73.61	82.67	66.34	61.63	76.35	51.67	71.67	91.11	59.07	63.46	80.87	52.22	67.59	82.75	57.32
GLTR	65.51	60.10	72.00	66.34	61.03	72.67	65.81	63.65	68.13	64.68	56.73	75.22	65.59	60.38	72.01

TABLE 5. Average Original F1-Score, Precision (P), and Recall (R) across domains for setting 2. Models sorted by overall average Original F1-score. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R
SFT-2D-to-7D	97.99	98.22	97.78	94.01	93.11	95.22	97.34	96.90	97.82	92.88	94.50	91.78	95.56	95.68	95.65
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	97.83	96.40	99.33	90.55	85.99	96.33	96.14	94.12	98.40	93.70	93.37	94.67	94.56	92.47	97.18
SFT-7D-to-2D	97.80	96.96	98.67	90.71	85.33	97.44	96.07	93.99	98.36	92.60	92.75	92.74	94.30	92.26	96.80
MultiDomain	96.90	98.17	95.78	90.96	93.27	89.89	95.51	96.30	95.02	90.92	94.45	88.45	93.57	95.55	92.28
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	96.04	93.45	98.89	89.58	82.75	98.22	95.26	92.10	98.85	92.64	88.83	97.48	93.38	89.28	98.36
DualDomain	96.39	97.14	95.78	87.36	81.65	95.56	94.20	93.97	94.93	82.90	95.11	77.93	90.21	91.97	91.05
SingleDomain	89.50	89.53	89.56	78.55	68.92	92.33	87.45	83.59	92.13	84.71	84.58	85.26	85.05	81.65	89.82
Binoculars	88.11	86.31	90.22	63.51	93.37	53.00	86.19	93.10	80.98	69.24	76.96	65.26	76.76	87.44	72.36
RADAR	72.71	68.08	78.22	67.31	59.33	79.00	72.41	66.13	81.20	70.68	62.36	85.04	70.78	63.98	80.86
e5	76.48	77.69	77.11	70.98	75.11	70.00	75.28	77.53	75.07	49.18	62.74	48.22	67.98	73.27	67.60
GLTR	61.97	60.48	69.33	50.34	60.64	49.78	58.32	63.52	61.47	63.41	58.06	78.22	58.51	60.68	64.70

alization. As shown in Table 5, the SFT-2D-to-7D strategy emerges as the most robust (Avg F1: 95.56%), suggesting that a curriculum learning approach—solidifying domain knowledge on a smaller set before expanding—creates a more adaptable decision boundary for unseen generators. Notably, even our simplest SingleDomain LLM (F1: 85.05%) outperforms all baselines, including the supervised e5 and zero-shot methods. This indicates that fine-tuning an LLM on any machine-generated text allows it to learn generalized features (e.g., lack of specific phrasing patterns) that transfer effectively to outputs generated by models like Gemini or Claude. In contrast, zero-shot methods like Binoculars, while precise under specific attacks, suffer from low overall recall, failing to flag content from these newer, more advanced generators. Consistent with Setting 1, Spelling Variations act as a discriminator between robust and brittle models: while e5 collapses (F1 < 50%), fine-tuned LLMs remain largely unaffected, reinforcing the value of their semantic pre-training.

The gap between Greedy and Sampling decoding further clarifies the models' limitations. Under Greedy decoding (Table 6), most models perform well, with DPO variants achieving near-perfect recall (99.8%). This suggests that deterministic AI text, regardless of the source model, shares com-

mon, easily detectable traits. However, Sampling decoding (Table 7) exposes the fragility of traditional baselines when faced with higher entropy text from novel models. Binoculars sees a drastic performance drop of over 16 percentage points (F1_G 85.69% → F1_S 69.39%), indicating it struggles to distinguish human creativity from the randomized output of a sampled AI model. Conversely, our fine-tuned LLMs demonstrate remarkable stability (e.g., SFT-2D-to-7D drops only ~3%), suggesting that they have internalized a robust concept of “machine-generated” that holds true even when the generator’s output distribution is randomized.

F. SETTING 3

Setting 3 (Unseen Domains/Unseen Models) represents the most challenging “in-the-wild” scenario, where the detector encounters both topics and generator models entirely unknown during training. As shown in Tables 8, 9 and 10, this setting clearly distinguishes the generalization limits of different approaches.

Table 8 highlights a critical threshold for generalization: Multi-Domain Training. While SingleDomain LLMs struggle here (F1: 72.90%), failing to generalize effectively to completely new distributions, the DualDomain and MultiDomain strategies maintain highly competitive performance

TABLE 6. Average F1-Greedy Score (F1_G), Precision (P), and Recall-Greedy (R_G) across domains for setting 2. Models sorted by overall average F1_G. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G
SFT-2D-to-7D	99.10	98.22	100.00	95.60	93.11	98.22	98.38	96.90	99.91	95.53	94.50	96.59	97.15	95.68	98.68
MultiDomain	98.42	98.17	98.67	93.19	93.27	93.11	97.08	96.30	97.87	93.89	94.45	93.33	95.64	95.55	95.74
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	98.17	96.40	100.00	91.50	85.99	97.78	96.89	94.12	99.82	95.45	93.37	97.63	95.50	92.47	98.81
SFT-7D-to-2D	98.46	96.96	100.00	91.42	85.33	98.45	96.61	93.99	99.38	94.28	92.75	95.85	95.19	92.26	98.42
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	96.62	93.45	100.00	90.47	82.75	99.78	95.89	92.10	100.00	93.95	88.83	99.70	94.23	89.28	99.87
DualDomain	97.68	97.14	98.22	88.62	81.65	96.89	95.45	93.97	96.98	88.62	95.11	82.96	92.59	91.97	93.76
Binoculars	92.46	86.31	99.56	79.87	93.37	69.77	94.09	93.10	95.11	76.33	76.96	75.70	85.69	87.44	85.04
SingleDomain	89.21	89.53	88.89	78.23	68.92	90.45	87.79	83.59	92.44	85.68	84.58	86.82	85.23	81.65	89.65
RADAR	75.03	68.08	83.56	69.08	59.33	82.67	74.95	66.13	86.49	73.20	62.36	88.59	73.06	63.98	85.33
e5	79.25	77.69	80.89	73.41	75.11	71.78	78.14	77.53	78.75	55.97	62.74	50.52	71.69	73.27	70.48
GLTR	69.05	60.48	80.44	61.31	60.64	62.00	67.77	63.52	72.62	69.15	58.06	85.48	66.82	60.68	75.14

TABLE 7. Average F1-Sampling Score (F1_S), Precision (P), and Recall-Sampling (R_S) across domains for setting 2. Models sorted by overall average F1_S. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S
SFT-2D-to-7D	96.87	98.22	95.56	92.66	93.11	92.22	96.31	96.90	95.73	90.57	94.50	86.96	94.11	95.68	92.62
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	97.52	96.40	98.67	90.22	85.99	94.89	95.53	94.12	96.98	92.53	93.37	91.70	93.95	92.47	95.56
SFT-7D-to-2D	97.15	96.96	97.33	90.54	85.33	96.45	95.63	93.99	97.33	91.16	92.75	89.63	93.62	92.26	95.19
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	95.57	93.45	97.78	89.17	82.75	96.67	94.81	92.10	97.69	91.93	88.83	95.26	92.87	89.28	96.85
MultiDomain	95.46	98.17	92.89	89.85	93.27	86.67	94.19	96.30	92.18	88.67	94.45	83.56	92.04	95.55	88.82
DualDomain	95.20	97.14	93.33	87.49	81.65	94.22	93.43	93.97	92.89	82.53	95.11	72.89	89.66	91.97	88.33
SingleDomain	89.87	89.53	90.22	79.61	68.92	94.22	87.51	83.59	91.82	84.14	84.58	83.70	85.28	81.65	89.99
RADAR	70.40	68.08	72.89	66.38	59.33	75.33	70.69	66.13	75.91	70.65	62.36	81.48	69.53	63.98	76.40
Binoculars	83.51	86.31	80.89	52.20	93.37	36.22	77.82	93.10	66.85	64.03	76.96	54.82	69.39	87.44	59.69
e5	75.45	77.69	73.33	71.50	75.11	68.22	74.33	77.53	71.38	53.03	62.74	45.93	68.58	73.27	64.72
GLTR	59.33	60.48	58.22	46.39	60.64	37.56	56.15	63.52	50.31	63.87	58.06	70.96	56.43	60.68	54.26

(>91% F1). This suggests that exposure to even just two diverse domains (Abstracts + Reddit) during fine-tuning is sufficient to break the model’s reliance on domain-specific features, allowing it to learn invariant markers of AI generation. Compared to baselines, the gap is stark: e5-small suffers significantly from domain shift and adversarial attacks (Spelling variation F1 drops to 56%), confirming that supervised encoder models struggle to adapt to unseen distributions without massive training data. Zero-shot methods like Binoculars also falter, particularly under Semantic Variations, where their F1 score collapses by over 25 points. In contrast, our SFT-2D-to-7D model demonstrates robust generalization (F1: 95.25%), effectively bridging the gap between seen and unseen worlds.

The analysis of decoding strategies further reinforces the stability of fine-tuned LLMs. Under Greedy decoding (Table 9), DPO-enhanced models achieve near-perfect recall (99.75%), effectively acting as a “safety net” that catches almost all deterministic AI text, regardless of topic or source. When facing Sampling decoding (Table 10), the robustness of our approach becomes even more evident. While Binoculars suffers a sharp decline in performance (dropping ~10 percentage points from Greedy to Sampling), our top LLM models show minimal degradation (e.g., SFT-2D-to-7D drops

only ~1.3%). This stability implies that fine-tuned LLMs have learned to detect deep structural patterns of AI generation that are independent of both the semantic topic (Domain) and the specific sampling parameters (Generation Strategy), a capability that zero-shot and simple supervised baselines lack in this challenging context.

1) Statistical significance

To rigorously validate the reliability of our results in the most challenging scenario (Setting 3), we performed McNemar’s statistical significance test comparing the classification outcomes of our best-performing model (SFT-2D-to-7D) against the top baseline (*Binoculars*) on the full setting 3. The test yielded a statistic of $\chi^2 = 1050.18$ ($p < 0.001$). This confirms that the superior performance of the fine-tuned LLM is statistically significant and robust.

2) Statistical reliability and confidence intervals

To assess the statistical reliability of our findings and quantify performance variability due to sample composition, we computed 95% Confidence Intervals (CI) using empirical bootstrapping. Specifically, we analyzed the predictions of our top-performing configuration, the SFT-2D-to-7D model, on the challenging Setting 3 test set ($N = 13, 200$).

TABLE 8. Average Original F1-Score, Precision (P), and Recall (R) across domains for setting 3. Models sorted by overall average Original F1-score. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R
SFT-2D-to-7D	97.16	95.29	99.16	93.25	90.90	96.25	96.69	94.38	99.20	93.90	93.63	94.56	95.25	93.55	97.29
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	97.05	94.81	99.50	92.40	89.58	95.75	96.45	93.99	99.13	93.42	95.03	92.61	94.83	93.35	96.75
SFT-7D-to-2D	97.65	95.75	99.66	91.36	87.21	96.58	96.25	93.47	99.30	93.34	92.98	93.89	94.65	92.35	97.36
MultiDomain	96.97	95.64	98.34	90.89	91.90	90.50	96.34	94.71	98.07	92.32	93.45	91.61	94.13	93.93	94.63
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	95.49	91.73	99.66	91.15	85.41	98.33	94.74	90.36	99.77	93.22	88.88	98.22	93.65	89.10	99.00
DualDomain	96.30	94.47	98.33	89.70	85.54	95.25	94.89	92.92	97.17	83.69	94.03	79.56	91.14	91.74	92.58
Binoculars	87.70	83.13	93.17	62.31	86.23	55.58	88.18	88.90	88.27	64.30	69.74	64.61	75.62	82.00	75.41
e5	83.64	79.97	88.00	79.39	78.80	81.00	83.15	80.26	86.67	56.12	65.32	57.17	75.58	76.09	78.21
SingleDomain	75.19	70.28	82.83	70.35	59.46	87.83	76.31	67.79	89.07	69.76	65.67	76.83	72.90	65.80	84.14
GLTR	73.38	65.09	86.17	58.01	63.70	58.92	69.19	66.83	74.93	71.12	61.20	88.17	67.93	64.21	77.05
RADAR	67.11	53.14	91.84	64.98	50.20	92.58	67.39	53.04	93.43	67.10	52.30	94.56	66.64	52.17	93.10

TABLE 9. Average F1-Greedy Score (F1_G), Precision (P), and Recall-Greedy (R_G) across domains for setting 3. Models sorted by overall average F1_G. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G
SFT-2D-to-7D	97.59	95.29	100.00	94.32	90.90	98.00	97.04	94.38	99.87	95.07	93.63	96.56	96.00	93.55	98.61
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	97.34	94.81	100.00	93.22	89.58	97.17	96.74	93.99	99.67	95.40	95.03	95.78	95.67	93.35	98.15
SFT-7D-to-2D	97.83	95.75	100.00	92.07	87.21	97.50	96.50	93.47	99.73	94.90	92.98	96.89	95.32	92.35	98.53
MultiDomain	97.45	95.64	99.33	92.53	91.90	93.17	96.78	94.71	98.93	94.00	93.45	94.55	95.19	93.93	96.50
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	95.69	91.73	100.00	91.99	85.41	99.67	94.94	90.36	100.00	93.82	88.88	99.33	94.11	89.10	99.75
DualDomain	97.00	94.47	99.67	90.84	85.54	96.84	95.58	92.92	98.40	88.36	94.03	83.33	92.94	91.74	94.56
Binoculars	90.24	83.13	98.67	76.76	86.23	69.17	92.41	88.90	96.20	69.54	69.74	69.33	82.24	82.00	83.34
e5	85.27	79.97	91.34	81.24	78.80	83.83	84.82	80.26	89.93	62.30	65.32	59.56	78.41	76.09	81.16
SingleDomain	75.97	70.28	82.67	70.42	59.46	86.33	77.06	67.79	89.27	71.21	65.67	77.78	73.67	65.80	84.01
GLTR	77.03	65.09	94.34	64.91	63.70	66.17	74.67	66.83	84.60	74.24	61.20	94.33	72.71	64.21	84.86
RADAR	68.24	53.14	95.33	65.41	50.20	93.83	68.24	53.04	95.67	67.90	52.30	96.78	67.45	52.17	95.40

Over 1,000 bootstrap iterations, the model exhibited a remarkably tight standard deviation of $\pm 0.18\%$ and a 95% Confidence Interval of [94.95%, 95.67%]. This narrow interval indicates that the reported performance is stable with respect to variations in the test sample distribution.

G. SETTING 4

Setting 4 tests generalization to unseen domains using seen AI models. LLM-based models clearly outperform baselines, especially under attacks where baseline performance often collapses, while proposed methods demonstrate remarkable robustness. Results are shown in Tables 11, 12 and 13.

The performance disparity between SingleDomain and Multi-Domain models provides a clear lesson on overfitting (Tables 11). SingleDomain (F1: 75.70%) likely learns to associate “AI-generated” labels with specific vocabulary (e.g., scientific terms from Abstracts), causing it to fail when faced with Medical or Financial jargon, even if the generator is familiar. In contrast, Multi-Domain and SFT-7-to-2-DPO models achieve high performance (Avg F1: $\sim 94.90\%$), indicating that training on diverse topics forces the model to unlearn specific vocabulary and focus on structural syntax and stylistic invariants common to the generating models. Comparing baselines, Spelling Variations again serve as a

stress test: e5 and Binoculars show significant instability, whereas fine-tuned LLMs remain robust. This confirms that even when the AI generator is “known”, simple surface-level noise is enough to break traditional detectors if they haven’t learned deep semantic robustness.

The comparison between Greedy and Sampling decoding highlights distinct trade-offs in baseline behaviors. Under Greedy decoding (Table 12), even weaker baselines like RADAR achieve extremely high recall (99.43%), but at the cost of precision, effectively flagging too many false positives. This suggests they struggle to pinpoint the specific decision boundary when the domain changes. The Sampling results (Table 13) further clarify the superior stability of fine-tuned LLMs. While Binoculars exhibits a characteristic “brittleness” to sampling noise (dropping from $\sim 86\%$ F1_G to $\sim 71\%$ F1_S) and GLTR struggles similarly, our SFT-7-to-2-DPO model maintains consistent performance (dropping only $\sim 1.9\%$). This indicates that our approach successfully balances the trade-off: it retains the high recall needed to catch known generators (like RADAR) while maintaining the high precision and robustness to sampling noise (unlike Binoculars), regardless of the semantic domain.

To complement the tabular results, Figure 5 provides a visual summary of the average F1-scores across the four

TABLE 10. Average F1-Sampling Score (F1_S), Precision (P), and Recall-Sampling (R_S) across domains for setting 3. Models sorted by overall average F1_S. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S
SFT-2D-to-7D	96.79	95.29	98.34	92.67	90.90	94.50	96.41	94.38	98.54	93.09	93.63	92.56	94.74	93.55	95.98
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	96.86	94.81	99.00	91.89	89.58	94.34	96.24	93.99	98.60	92.15	95.03	89.44	94.29	93.35	95.35
SFT-7D-to-2D	97.51	95.75	99.34	91.24	87.21	95.67	96.09	93.47	98.87	91.92	92.98	90.89	94.19	92.35	96.19
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	95.38	91.73	99.34	90.84	85.41	97.00	94.73	90.36	99.53	92.81	88.88	97.11	93.44	89.10	98.24
MultiDomain	96.48	95.64	97.33	89.82	91.90	87.83	95.94	94.71	97.20	90.99	93.45	88.67	93.31	93.93	92.76
DualDomain	95.72	94.47	97.00	89.42	85.54	93.67	94.40	92.92	95.93	83.92	94.03	75.78	90.87	91.74	90.59
e5	82.25	79.97	84.67	78.48	78.80	78.17	81.80	80.26	83.40	59.59	65.32	54.78	75.53	76.09	75.25
SingleDomain	76.11	70.28	83.00	71.40	59.46	89.33	76.91	67.79	88.87	70.41	65.67	75.89	73.71	65.80	84.27
Binoculars	85.34	83.13	87.66	56.49	86.23	42.00	84.40	88.90	80.33	64.44	69.74	59.89	72.67	82.00	67.47
RADAR	66.36	53.14	88.34	64.79	50.20	91.33	67.07	53.04	91.20	66.78	52.30	92.33	66.25	52.17	90.80
GLTR	70.97	65.09	78.00	57.06	63.70	51.67	66.04	66.83	65.27	70.09	61.20	82.00	66.04	64.21	69.23

TABLE 11. Average Original F1-Score, Precision (P), and Recall (R) across domains for setting 4. Models sorted by overall average Original F1-score. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	96.68	95.14	98.34	92.22	89.24	95.67	96.01	94.38	97.77	94.68	94.71	94.94	94.90	93.37	96.68
SFT-2D-to-7D	96.09	94.76	97.50	91.86	90.79	93.33	96.20	94.44	98.10	94.33	93.31	95.50	94.62	93.33	96.11
MultiDomain	96.33	95.06	97.66	91.17	92.15	90.58	95.67	94.06	97.40	94.02	93.64	94.50	94.30	93.73	95.04
SFT-7D-to-2D	96.06	95.03	97.17	90.26	87.87	93.58	95.14	93.17	97.30	93.89	92.99	95.00	93.84	92.27	95.76
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	95.09	91.57	99.00	91.51	86.87	97.08	94.56	90.78	98.80	93.88	89.67	98.72	93.76	89.72	98.40
DualDomain	95.30	94.22	96.50	89.38	86.67	93.50	94.39	93.03	96.00	88.65	94.03	85.78	91.93	91.98	92.95
e5	86.02	79.76	94.16	83.25	77.81	90.34	86.08	80.12	93.80	59.98	73.74	63.16	78.83	77.86	85.37
Binoculars	87.10	85.11	89.33	68.31	86.72	62.25	86.92	90.28	84.47	69.45	79.70	65.50	77.95	85.45	75.39
GLTR	78.43	68.63	92.34	74.83	72.01	81.00	78.17	71.82	87.00	74.58	63.63	92.11	76.50	69.02	88.11
SingleDomain	77.18	68.45	90.34	72.94	60.71	93.25	77.69	66.88	94.60	74.97	66.88	86.83	75.70	65.73	91.25
RADAR	70.87	55.74	98.00	68.12	52.29	97.92	70.13	54.65	98.50	69.50	53.86	98.67	69.65	54.13	98.27

evaluation settings. For each method and setting, the reported value is computed as the mean of three complementary performance indicators: (i) the overall performance across all attacks and domains, (ii) the performance on texts generated via greedy decoding, and (iii) the performance on texts generated via sampling decoding. This aggregation offers a compact and informative comparison of the methods, facilitating the identification of consistent trends across settings and highlighting the robustness of the proposed approach under diverse generation conditions.

H. STABILITY AND WORST-CASE ANALYSIS

Beyond average metrics, it is crucial to examine the operational stability of detectors under adversarial pressure. High average scores can potentially obscure catastrophic failures in specific scenarios. To address this, we analyzed the performance dispersion across all 40 adversarial configurations in Setting 3 (4 domains × 10 attack conditions).

As visualized in **Figure 6**, there is a striking contrast in reliability between the proposed method and the zero-shot baseline. The *Binoculars* baseline (Red), despite a respectable average on clean text, proves highly unstable. The dispersion of data points reveals that its performance is brittle: simple character-level perturbations like **Homoglyphs**

cause the detector’s performance to degrade severely (e.g., dropping to 8.60% F1-score on the Finance domain). Similarly, **Synonym substitution** attacks degrade its performance to ~22-30% in several instances. This indicates that the zero-shot method relies on fragile token-probability patterns that are easily disrupted by surface-level noise.

Conversely, the fine-tuned **SFT-2D-to-7D** model (Green) demonstrates strong stability. Notably, the *worst-case* performance recorded for our model across the entire test suite is **84.98%** (under Homoglyph attacks on Finance), which is drastically higher than the baseline. Even under paraphrasing, the fine-tuned model retains high detection capabilities, focusing on the underlying semantic artifacts of AI generation rather than relying on brittle surface features. This confirms that the fine-tuned LLM offers a significantly more robust and reliable profile for real-world deployment.

I. DISCUSSION

The results consistently show that the proposed approach achieves strong and stable performance across all evaluation settings, including different attack scenarios and decoding strategies. Compared to existing methods discussed in Section III and summarized in Table 1, which often exhibit sensitivity to adversarial perturbations or limited generalization

TABLE 12. Average F1-Greedy Score (F1_G), Precision (P), and Recall-Greedy (R_G) across domains for setting 4. Models sorted by overall average F1_G. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G	F1_G	P	R_G
SFT-2D-to-7D	97.15	94.76	99.67	93.79	90.79	97.00	96.95	94.44	99.60	95.91	93.31	98.67	95.95	93.33	98.73
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	97.35	95.14	99.67	93.11	89.24	97.33	96.79	94.38	99.33	96.49	94.71	98.33	95.94	93.37	98.67
MultiDomain	97.31	95.06	99.67	93.39	92.15	94.67	96.72	94.06	99.53	95.61	93.64	97.67	95.76	93.73	97.88
SFT-7D-to-2D	96.97	95.03	99.00	91.68	87.87	95.83	95.81	93.17	98.60	95.32	92.99	97.78	94.95	92.27	97.80
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	95.45	91.57	99.67	92.39	86.87	98.67	94.96	90.78	99.53	94.46	89.67	99.78	94.31	89.72	99.41
DualDomain	96.39	94.22	98.67	90.95	86.67	95.67	95.32	93.03	97.73	92.60	94.03	91.22	93.82	91.98	95.82
Binoculars	91.53	85.11	99.00	84.03	86.72	81.50	93.83	90.28	97.67	77.52	79.70	75.44	86.73	85.45	88.40
e5	88.08	79.76	98.33	85.82	77.81	95.67	88.21	80.12	98.13	69.84	73.74	66.33	82.99	77.86	89.62
GLTR	81.18	68.63	99.33	80.85	72.01	92.17	82.80	71.82	97.73	77.30	63.63	98.45	80.53	69.02	96.92
SingleDomain	78.61	68.45	92.33	73.72	60.71	93.83	78.81	66.88	95.93	76.85	66.88	90.33	77.00	65.73	93.11
RADAR	71.49	55.74	99.67	68.48	52.29	99.17	70.47	54.65	99.20	69.93	53.86	99.67	70.09	54.13	99.43

TABLE 13. Average F1-Sampling Score (F1_S), Precision (P), and Recall-Sampling (R_S) across domains for setting 4. Models sorted by overall average F1_S. Best value per column in bold.

Model	No Attack			Semantic Var.			Format Mod.			Spelling Var.			Overall Avg		
	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S	F1_S	P	R_S
SFT-7-to-2-DPO	96.06	95.14	97.00	91.56	89.24	94.00	95.28	94.38	96.20	93.11	94.71	91.56	94.00	93.37	94.69
SFT-2D-to-7D	95.05	94.76	95.33	90.23	90.79	89.67	95.51	94.44	96.60	92.82	93.31	92.33	93.40	93.33	93.48
SFT-2-to-7-DPO	94.83	91.57	98.33	90.98	86.87	95.50	94.29	90.78	98.07	93.50	89.67	97.67	93.40	89.72	97.39
SFT-7D-to-2D	95.18	95.03	95.33	89.57	87.87	91.33	94.57	93.17	96.00	92.60	92.99	92.22	92.98	92.27	93.72
MultiDomain	95.36	95.06	95.67	89.24	92.15	86.50	94.66	94.06	95.27	92.47	93.64	91.33	92.93	93.73	92.19
DualDomain	94.27	94.22	94.33	88.94	86.67	91.34	93.64	93.03	94.27	86.64	94.03	80.33	90.87	91.98	90.07
e5	84.57	79.76	90.00	81.25	77.81	85.00	84.53	80.12	89.47	66.16	73.74	60.00	79.13	77.86	81.12
SingleDomain	77.13	68.45	88.33	73.36	60.71	92.67	77.90	66.88	93.27	74.20	66.88	83.33	75.65	65.73	89.40
GLTR	76.08	68.63	85.33	70.90	72.01	69.83	73.98	71.82	76.27	73.06	63.63	85.78	73.50	69.02	79.30
Binoculars	82.30	85.11	79.66	57.49	86.72	43.00	79.65	90.28	71.27	65.47	79.70	55.56	71.23	85.45	62.37
RADAR	70.62	55.74	96.34	67.87	52.29	96.67	70.12	54.65	97.80	69.43	53.86	97.67	69.51	54.13	97.12
Average	87.40	83.95	92.33	81.03	80.28	85.05	86.74	83.96	91.32	81.77	81.47	84.34	84.24	82.42	88.26

across domains and generators, our approach demonstrates improved robustness and consistency.

In particular, zero-shot methods such as Binoculars, RADAR, and GLTR show significant performance degradation under adversarial manipulations and sampling-based generation, confirming their limited robustness and reliance on surface-level statistical patterns. Similarly, supervised encoder-based approaches (e.g., e5-small) exhibit strong performance in controlled settings but suffer from reduced generalization under domain shift and spelling perturbations, as also highlighted in prior literature.

In contrast, the proposed fine-tuned LLM-based detectors maintain stable performance across all evaluation conditions, including unseen domains, unseen generators, and diverse attack types. This suggests that the adopted sequential fine-tuning strategies enable the model to capture more invariant characteristics of AI-generated text, going beyond token-level or model-specific artifacts.

These observations directly support the research questions formulated in Section II, confirming that addressing robustness, cross-domain generalization, and fine-tuning strategies is critical for reliable AI-generated text detection. Overall, the results provide empirical evidence that carefully designed

fine-tuning pipelines can significantly improve the practical applicability of LLM-based detectors in real-world scenarios. These findings position fine-tuned LLM-based detectors as a practical and scalable solution for real-world AI-generated text detection, particularly in adversarial and dynamically evolving environments.

IX. CONCLUSION AND LIMITATIONS

Beyond aggregate performance gains, the study provides concrete guidance on selecting fine-tuning strategies depending on operational priorities (e.g., recall-oriented detection via DPO versus precision-oriented detection via multi-stage SFT) and expected domain variability. This work has confirmed the remarkable potential of LLM-based methodologies for identifying AI-generated text. Our results indicate that these approaches can outperform conventional methods, with multi-domain training emerging as the primary strategy for developing robust detectors. Our findings offer valuable insights for the real-world deployment of AI text detectors. The demonstrated robustness of multi-domain, multi-stage fine-tuned LLMs is particularly relevant, as real-world systems must contend with a constant stream of novel content from diverse sources and evasion attempts like paraphrasing.

FIGURE 5. Average F1-score for each method across the four evaluation settings. For each setting, the plotted value is obtained by averaging the overall F1 reported in the three corresponding result tables, namely the overall F1, F1_G, and F1_S values.

FIGURE 6. Stability Analysis showing F1-Score Dispersion by Attack Category (Setting 3). The box plots illustrate the distribution of performance across all domains and specific attacks within each category. Each dot represents a specific domain-attack pair. The fine-tuned LLM (SFT-2D-to-7D, Green) exhibits a tight, high-performance cluster with a minimum score above 84%, indicating strong reliability. In contrast, the baseline (Binoculars, Red) shows significant instability in Spelling and Semantic categories, with several data points dropping below 30% (e.g., Homoglyph and Synonym failures), highlighting severe vulnerability to specific adversarial manipulations.

For instance, a platform for academic integrity could leverage a DPO-tuned model to minimize false negatives (i.e., failing to flag AI-generated text), prioritizing high recall. Conversely, a content moderation system might prefer a model with higher precision to avoid incorrectly flagging human-written text. Our comprehensive evaluation across different attack types and generalization settings provides a practical guide for selecting the most suitable strategy based on the specific requirements.

However, deploying these systems presents significant challenges. The use of an 8-billion parameter model, even when quantized, entails substantial computational costs and latency, which can be a bottleneck for real-time applications. Future work should therefore explore knowledge distillation to transfer the capabilities of these large detectors into smaller, more efficient models. Furthermore, the rapid evolution of generative models necessitates a dynamic approach to detection. Systems must be continuously re-evaluated and updated through a robust Machine Learning Operations (MLOps) pipeline to maintain their effectiveness over time. Despite these encouraging results, several critical areas warrant further investigation. The research was limited to the English language, leaving its cross-linguistic validity undetermined; future investigations should therefore explore the transferability of a model trained in English to other languages versus the need for language-specific fine-tuning, particularly for languages with unique grammatical structures. Indeed, while the fine-tuning methodologies explored are language-agnostic in principle, the effectiveness of an AI text detector is deeply related to the statistical patterns of a specific language and the artifacts introduced by models pre-training. Generalizing our findings to other languages is not easy and presents several challenges:

- Grammatical structures, syntactic rules, and stylistic conventions vary significantly across languages. A detector trained on English might fail to capture the subtle differences of AI-generation in a language with a different morphological or syntactic structure.
- The performance of our approach relies on a base model (Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct) and multi-domain training data. The availability of comparable resources differs greatly across languages, potentially impacting the feasibility and effectiveness of this method.

Future work should therefore investigate the cross-lingual transferability of our English-trained detectors and, more importantly, develop and evaluate detectors specifically fine-tuned on native-language models and corpora. This will require the creation of new multilingual benchmarks to enable a rigorous evaluation.

Due to significant computational constraints, each fine-tuning experiment was conducted only once. While we ensured the reproducibility of each specific run by fixing the random seed, we did not assess the performance variance across multiple seeds. The fine-tuning process contains stochastic elements, such as the initialization of LoRA

adapters and data shuffling, which can lead to minor variations in final model performance. At the same time, several elements partially mitigate this limitation. First, our study includes multiple independently trained LLM-based configurations (e.g., SFT, SFT+DPO, and multi-stage SFT), which differ in training pipelines, domain compositions, and sequential fine-tuning strategies. Although these models share the same backbone (Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct), they are exposed to partially different training data and optimization trajectories. While these configurations do not constitute repeated runs of the same setup, the consistency of performance trends observed across all configurations and evaluation settings suggests that the reported results capture stable properties of the approach rather than isolated outcomes of a single training instance. Future work should conduct experiments over multiple random seeds to provide more robust estimates of performance and quantify the stability of the fine-tuning process.

Furthermore, regarding the threshold strategy, our results indicate that a single global threshold is not only practical for real-world deployment (where the text's origin is often unknown) but also offers superior generalization compared to domain-specific thresholds, which are prone to overfitting when calibrated on smaller optimization subsets. Similarly, future work will need to address current blind spots, such as the system's effectiveness on shorter text fragments and its resilience against sophisticated, layered adversarial tactics that combine multiple attack techniques. Finally, although our comparative analysis of fine-tuning strategies was conducted rigorously using Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct, it is crucial to verify that these observed principles hold true across a broader landscape of architectures and model sizes. Subsequent studies should therefore aim to replicate these results with both larger models and smaller, more resource-efficient alternatives to ensure that this detection methodology is not only effective but also widely scalable for practical applications. Finally, we must acknowledge the inherent limitations of pure text-based detection paradigms. As generative models continue to evolve, the linguistic distribution of AI text will increasingly overlap with human writing, potentially establishing an upper bound on the theoretical accuracy of post-hoc classifiers. In real-world deployments, fine-tuned LLM detectors should not operate in isolation: they should be integrated into multi-layered mitigation frameworks. Combining our text-based detection with alternative strategies such as provider-side watermarking, verifiable cryptographic provenance (metadata tracking), and human-in-the-loop moderation will be essential to establish a comprehensive and resilient defense against AI-generated disinformation.

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